

HIGH TEMPERATURE STABLE CERAMIC COMPOSITES DERIVED FROM NANO-METALLOPOLYCARBOSILANE AND NANO-METALLOPOLY(BORO)SILAZANE PRECURSORS

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SUMMARY: Polycarbosilanes (PCS) and SiBCN-precursors were chosen for the fabrication of high temperature ceramics in this study. An intermediate polysilane (PS) was synthesized by the Wurtz-reaction and transformed thermally to PCS. In addition molecular compounds with varying Si:B-ratios were prepared by the hydroboration of vinyl silanes. In order to introduce metals into the Si(B)C(N)-polymers appropriate organometallic compounds were selected from compounds of the general formula R_nMX_q , where R = organic substituent, M = transition metal from group 4 to 7, X = another oxygen-free ligand or CO. Optimized conditions for the synthesis and processing were determined. Intermediate and final products were analyzed by NMR-, UV-, IR-spectroscopy, GC, GC-MS, HPLC, XRD, EXAFS, chemical analysis and TGA-MS. Complete separation of the ligands from the metal atom was found in some cases. The metal compounds decomposed to form nano-particles which are enclosed in the polymeric matrix.

KEYWORDS: polymer, ceramic, processing, metal-modified precursors, SiBCN-polymers, nano-particles.

INTRODUCTION

Ceramic composites with an ultra fine microstructure usually show very good mechanical properties. The formation of ceramics via polymer pyrolysis often gives X-ray

amorphous structures with crystallite sizes of 2 to 8 nm. But at temperatures higher than 1500 – 1600 K the grains begin to grow rapidly reducing the strength. So ceramic fibres for long-term high temperature applications up to 1800-1900 K require special stabilisation. It is common practice to stabilize ceramic structures with heteroatoms of many metals from group 3 to 7 of the Periodic Table. Most advantageous are high melting elements (Ti, Zr, Hf, B etc.), that give an improvement of thermal resistance and sintering activity. The introduction of metals into the ceramic structure is a rather difficult task, because a nearly ideal homogeneous distribution of the metal particles in the solid structure and no additional introduction of oxygen is required. The chemical method, which is presently applied industrially by “Ube Inds”(Japan), uses tetraethoxyalkyls of titanium, acetylacetonate of zirconium and alumoxan to stabilise the fibres. This process is far from ideal for oxygen-free ceramics, because the introduced metals form bonds to backbone elements of the polymer through oxygen, generally in the form of Si-O-M units. Its removal at high temperature is harmful for the ceramic structure or rather complicated.

In this work we present a new and more effective method for the preparation and stabilisation of CMCs. High melting metals are introduced into precursor polymers in a cluster or nano particle form. The metal particles are produced by fast thermodestruction of special organometallic compounds in the solution or melt of the polymer or, and that is the most important point, *in situ* during the process of polymerisation. This has the following advantages: 1) no additional oxygen; 2) high chemical activity of metal nano particles and precursors for improving the polymer structure and ceramic yield; 3) more economical manufacturing. The distribution of the metal nano particles in the polymer and in the ceramic products is very homogeneous and comparable to traditional chemical methods.

Previously, organic linear monophase metallopolymers have been prepared in Russia, for example, metallopolyethylene [1-3]. Nano-particles of metals were formed in a hot solution or in the melt of polymers. These investigations indicate that metal clusters are introduced into the vacancies, which arise during the packing of polymer molecules. Small angle X-ray scattering of samples containing 1 to 7 mass-% of iron in the polyethylene gives particle sizes of 0.5 to 7.5 nm. A separate metal phase is absent.

These results prompted the authors to develop a new method for the syntheses of metallopolymer precursors for high quality ceramics. The major task is the fabrication of oxygen free composite ceramics of Si-C and Si-(B)-C-N types. Polymeric and oligomeric precursors of polycarbosilanes and polycarbosilazanes were thus used for this study. It was found that these polymers demand the use of specific metals and organo-metallic compounds.

ORGANO-METALIC COMPOUNDS FOR THE GENERATION OF NANO-PARTICLES

The search for the most appropriate organo-metallic compounds (OMC) was conducted among the compounds of the general formula:

where R = an oxygen free organic ligand, M = a metal from groups 4 to 7 of the Periodic Table, and X = H, Cl or CO.

The classes of carbonyls, cyclopentadienyl complexes and metal alkyls were investigated, having in mind the following properties: 1) stability, 2) solubility in organic solvents, 3) nature of thermolysis products, 4) volatility and 5) availability.

It turned out that metal alkyls and primarily tetrabenzyls (TB) of metals are the most promising class of OMC, but many other compounds with other alkyl ligands can probably be used. Tetrabenzyls of titanium, zirconium and hafnium were compared. Their thermostability increases in this row from minus temperature to room temperature, the absence of light being desirable. According to this criteria the most appropriate compound could be tetrabenzyl hafnium, but its synthesis and availability is difficult [4-6].

From the cyclopentadienyl complexes Cp_2MX_2 (Cp = cyclopentadienyl, X = Cl, H, Me, Ph) only bis-cyclopentadienyldichlorides (BCDDCl) gave promising results. The thermal decomposition of these OMC occurs, however, around 573 K, which is rather low. Other complexes like $Cp_2Ti(H)_2$, $Cp_2Ti(CH_3)_2$, or $Cp_2Ti(C_6H_5)_2$ were also considered, but are more difficult to prepare and handle. The investigations show that metal carbonyls are too reactive in catalyzing the PS to PCS conversion. Undesirable decomposition reactions were observed as well as extreme crosslinking and polycondensation. Moreover, only a limited number of metals are really available in the form of carbonyls.

For the first experiments on the laboratory scale the following compounds were selected, their syntheses and purification were carried out: Cp_2ZrCl_2 , Cp_2TiCl_2 , $TiBz_4$, $ZrBz_4$ (Bz = benzyl), $Fe(CO)_5$, $Mo(CO)_5(NCCH_3)$, $Re_2(CO)_{10}$, and $Ti(BH_4)_3$. The tetrachlorides $TiCl_4$ and $ZrCl_4$ were used for comparison in order to examine the influence of chlorine. The PCS containing iron nano-particles (NFePCS), derived from ironpentacarbonyl was used purely as a model to study the properties of metal in the polymer with Mössbauer spectroscopy. For more detailed experiments concerning the new fabrication method of nano-metallopolymer precursors the following OMC were chosen:

As was established earlier [7] a radical-chain mechanism is the primary thermal decomposition process of OMC:

where M^* = "hot" metal atom.

NANO-METALLOPOLYCARBOSILANES

For the polymer synthesis the classical Yajima process to form polycarbosilanes (PCS) was used [8]. It includes the synthesis of an intermediate polysilane (PS) from a chlorosilane by the Wurtz-reaction and then the transformation to PCS by thermal rearrangement and polycondensation. Some important methodical improvements of this method were developed to avoid oxygen incorporation in the final product. The results of using this method for the syntheses of nano-metallopolycarbosilanes (NMPCS) were partially reported [9].

PCS has a low molecular mass ($MM = 1200 - 2000$) and contains active Si-H and Si-Si bonds (at intermediate stages of the synthesis). So, as a matrix, it differs considerably from polyethylene. It was interesting to investigate the role of metal clusters in the process of PDMS to PCS transformation:

Intermediate and end products were analyzed by NMR-, UV-, IR-spectroscopy, GC (gas chromatography), GC-MS and HPLC (high pressure liquid chromatography). As a metal source bis-cyclopentadienyldichlorides of Ti and Zr were used. These compounds decompose at temperatures below 573 K.

If the reaction is carried out in the presence of Ti or Zr, the reaction time can be reduced from 25-28 to 3-5 hours (even at lower temperature). After the metal is introduced, the reaction rate increases without any negative side-effects. The Si-Si fragments completely disappear, and no insoluble or high fusible products are formed. We suppose that this phenomenon is caused by a catalytic effect of the metallic nano-particles. They can act as centers of branching of macromolecules without the participation of Si-H groups. The introduction of the metals at an intermediate stage of the synthesis (Kumada-rearrangement), when some of the initial Si-Si bonds of PDMS are still present, is most effective. The study showed that the nano-particles are involved in rearrangement and polycondensation reactions.

The new method provides nearly the same metal content, no additional oxygen content, a more regular polymer structure (higher ratio of $\text{HSi}^*\text{C}_3/\text{Si}^*\text{C}_4$) and a larger number of Si-H-groups compared to the traditional metallopolymers (fabricated with oxygen containing organotitanium- and organoboron-compounds). The molecular-mass distribution (MMD) is very close to the best PCS, which was fabricated by the very expensive autoclave method: a narrow unimodal MMD with a polydispersity index (M_w/M_n) of about 2. The average molecular mass is in the range from 1000 to 1200. High molecular mass components (tails) are absent. According to the rheological characteristics, NMPCS can be used for melt spinning at lower temperatures in comparison with the unmodified PCS. A viscosity of about 1000 Pa.s is achieved at 130-150 °C instead of 250-280 °C. The preliminary data showed that a metal content up to 3 mass. % does not prevent stable spinning of fibers.

The PCS samples with 5 mass % Fe were investigated by X-ray emission and Mössbauer spectroscopy. It was shown, that the PCS matrix does not differ from earlier investigated

polymers (e.g. polyethylene) with respect to the structure of nano-particles and their size distribution. It was found that more than 80% of the particles have diameters below 5 nm. All particles are composed of several phases: they contain Fe, iron carbide and iron oxide. The formation of FeSi was also detected. Strong Fe-C bonds between the nano-particles and the matrix were found in NFePCS as well as in other nano-metal polymers [9].

For further investigations tetrabenzyltitanium (TBT) and tetrabenzylzirconium (TBZ) were synthesized and purified. Taking the example of TBT, the complete separation of the ligands from the metal atom during the decomposition was shown by GC and GC-MS. The released radicals were stabilized forming quantitatively dibenzyl and toluene. Both compounds have been found in the distillation product in a ratio of 1:2 according to Eqn 3. Free of the original ligands the metal atoms (so-called "hot" atoms) form nano-particles and become the centers of polymer branching.

Table 1: Characteristic data of the metal-free polymer (oligomer) and NMPCS

No	Specimen index	OMC	H at Si, %	HSi*C ₃ /Si*C ₄ ratio(*)	M _n (**)	Polydispersity index
1	PCS	-	0,6-0,7	1	1500-2000	4
2	OCS	-	1,2-1,3	1,2-1,4	600-900	-
3	NZrPCS	Cp ₂ ZrCl ₂	0,9-1,0	1,1-1,2	1300-1400	2
4	NTiPCS	TiCl ₄	0,2-0,3	0,1-0,2	1800-4000	>7
5	NTiPCS	TiBz ₄	0,85-0,95	1,0-1,1	1250-1400	2

(*) determined by ²⁹Si NMR, (**) determined by GPC.

Table 1 shows the large difference in the structure and the content of Si-H groups in the obtained NMPCS. The use of TiCl₄ leads to the smallest content of Si-H groups, the use of TiBz₄ leads to a maximum of Si-H groups. Cp₂ZrCl₂ takes an intermediate place, but with quite satisfactory results. This shows the influence of chlorine, which requires a large input of Si-H groups to reduce the metal in the process of nano-particle formation. So the formation of undesirable hydrogen halides during thermolysis of PCS takes place.

At concentrations around 1,5-2,5 mass.% of metals and less than 1 mass. % of oxygen a slight stabilization of SiC can be seen by X-ray diffraction and TEM. An increase of ceramic yield was established by TGA examinations (62 mass. % for the metal free PCS, 66 – for NTiPCS and 71 – for NZrPCS) at 1500 °C (Fig. 1). The parallel DSC – analyses provided evidence for a difference between NTiPCS and NZrPCS. The heat treatment of the first material is accompanied by broad temperature range (450-850 K) where exothermic reactions occur. The

NZrPCS behaved less actively, with its energetic characteristics being similar to the metal free PCS. The very active catalytic action of Ti compounds was also detected during the syntheses of Ti-doped polymers. This effect requires further investigation.

Fig.1. TGA data on the PCS and the NMPCS.

1 – metal free PCS; 2 - NTiPCS (from TiBz_4); 3 - NZrPCS (from Cp_2ZrCl_2)
 (NETZSCH STA/QMS-System: 409/429-4; He; 400 °C - 10 °/min, 1450 °C - 2 °/min)

The investigation of the chemical bonding characteristics in Ti and Zr containing nano-MPCS with X-ray RED (X-ray Radial Electronic Density distribution technique) and the EXAFS (Extended X-rays Adsorption Fine Structure technique)[10] gave following results:

Experimental EXAFS data on interatomic distances (r) and coordination numbers (Z) for nano-ZrPCS show that the sample contains elemental zirconium (the interatomic distances of 3.11; 3.27; 5.58 Å coincide with calculated values). The peak with $r = 1.97$ Å can be assigned to Zr-C bonds and indicates strong interaction between the metal and the matrix. There is no ZrO_2 phase in the sample, since there are no peaks of Zr-Zr, Zr-O, which are characteristic for this phase.

Completely different results were obtained by EXAFS for nano-TiPCS: the sample contains both the metal phase and the oxide phase TiO_2 (probably anatase). The distance $r = 1.82$ Å possibly corresponds to Ti-C bonds arising from substitution of silicon atoms in the Si-C chains of the polymeric matrix. The X-ray diffraction study showed that all samples were X-ray amorphous. So the size of the crystallites (nano-particles) must be less than 20 Å.

A comparison of X-ray RED curves of nano-ZrPCS and nano-TiPCS with the data of the metal-free matrix polymer gave similar results. The obtained peaks for nano-ZrPCS correspond to the phase Zr^0 ($r = 3.20$; 5.60 Å). Again for the nano-TiPCS different characteristics were found: both the metal and the oxide phases are observed; the modeling of X-ray RED curves showed that the ratio between the phases Ti^0 and TiO_2 is 1:5. The formation of TiO_2 in the sample of nano-TiPCS is supported by XPS-analysis. The spectrum of $\text{Ti}2p_{3/2}$ consists of three

components, but for the chemical identification only two peaks have to be discussed: $E_b = 455.0$ eV and 459.2 eV. The last peak can be related to Ti-O bonds in titania or titanates quite reliably; the component with $E_b = 455.0$ eV seems to be attributed to Ti-C bonding. The modifications in the matrix during formation of MPCs are visible on the differential X-ray RED curves: strong disordering of bonds with lengths about 2 Å and 4-5 Å in the case of nano-TiPCS and nano-ZrPCS. This phenomenon is connected most likely with nano-MPCS formation. Rupture of the polymeric chains and their rearrangement combined with a distribution of the nano-particles in the bulk volume of the polymer might be the reason. XPS-analysis confirmed that there is no Ti or Zr on the surface of the investigated samples; this observation can be easily explained by an effect of encapsulation of metal nano-particles inside of cavities of the organic polymeric matrix.

The phase composition of nano-ZrPCS specimens was studied by EXAFS before and after heating. After heat treatment at 1100-1200 °C mainly $ZrSi_2$ was found. Additionally the peak with $r = 1.87$ Å can be assigned to Si-C containing phases. This conclusion is confirmed also by the XRD data. A very important result is the absence of the Zr-O phase. Nano-TiPCS showed a substantially different phase composition: after heat treatment Ti-C and Ti-O sites were detected.

The analyses of the new polymers are not yet finished. It is necessary to use other analytical methods including more exact oxygen analysis. Currently we use solid state MAS-NMR and high resolution TEM analyses to find out more details about the structure of the nano-MPCS.

NANO-METALLOPOLY(BORO)SILAZANES

During the last few years new ceramic polymer precursors in the Si-(B)-C-N system have been developed [11-12]. By optimisation of Si:B ratio ceramics stable up to very high temperature were fabricated. The application of these new precursor systems to ceramic matrices, coatings and fibers is a current topic in many laboratories. It seems very interesting to introduce nano-metal particles into SiBCN-polymers to enhance the chemical stability and mechanical strength at high temperature.

The SiBCN-compounds with different Si:B-ratios were prepared by hydroboration of vinyl silanes with boranes and chloroboranes. An example is shown in the following reaction scheme:

The molecular structure of one of the monomeric single source precursors was determined by single crystal X-ray diffraction. Subsequent ammonolysis of synthesised monomeric

precursors led to polymers with homogeneous distribution of all involved elements. The resulting novel starting materials were characterized by common analytical techniques like NMR, FTIR, MS and chemical analysis.

The thermal behaviour of the preceramic polymers was studied in detail. Ceramic yields were determined and volatile side products were identified by TGA-MS. High temperature TGA measurements in helium atmosphere showed that materials with B:Si-ratios of 1:2 and 1:3 are stable up to 1800°C. High temperature annealing experiments in varying atmospheres showed increased decomposition resistance of these materials compared to boron free silicon carbonitrides (Fig. 2). XRD measurements were conducted in order to investigate the crystallization behaviour of Si/B/C/N ceramics. Depending on the atmosphere as well as on the crucible material varying amounts of crystalline phases, namely SiC and Si₃N₄ were detected at 1600°C.

Fig. 2: Weight change of SiBCN ceramics during annealing at different temperatures under 0.1 MPa argon atmosphere.

Optimized conditions for the synthesis of metallo(boro)silazanes and their decomposition were developed in this study. Intermediate and final products were analyzed by NMR-, UV-, IR-spectroscopy, GC (gas chromatography), GC-MS and HPLC (high pressure liquid chromatography).

The introduction of zirconium nano-particles into Si_{3,0}B_{1,0}C_{9,3}N_{2,9}H_{25,3} was carried out by the addition of TBZ diethyl ether solution to the solution of polymer in para-xylene and applying UV-irradiation. 3-5% of zirconium was introduced, and the material was heat-treated at 1673 K. Structure and properties of the products are currently under examination using different methods of analyses (elements content, TGA-MS, TEM).

CONCLUSIONS

Precursor derived ceramics in the systems Si/C and Si/B/C/N containing metal nano-particles were successfully prepared by novel methods using transition metal complexes. The polymers as well as the ceramic products were characterized using several analytical techniques. Suitable transition metal compounds were found and the synthesis and processing of the materials was optimised. The polymeric and ceramic products are X-ray amorphous and contain the metal in the form of different phases.

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